

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D2.3 PM training toolkit VET certification strategy

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Author name(s):	Gabriela-Victoria Mnerie (ISIM), Nasos Panagiotidis (YET), Emilia Binchiciu (HELIX), Rosina Preis (EITM)
Reviewer(s):	Vassilis Tsoulis (YET), Katja Prinz (EITM)
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Section I:

Course description

PreMETS is an initiative under the ERASMUS+ framework, dedicated to advancing Predictive Maintenance (PM) methodologies. It addresses the current gap in PM education across industry, academia, and vocational training sectors. The project encompasses:

- Crafting cutting-edge educational kits tailored for PM students and educators.
- Forming a micro-credential certification system.
- Building an interdisciplinary portal that consolidates diverse PM materials.
- Aiming to educate:
 - 1,000 PM students;
 - 250 PM educators.

Within Work Package 2 (WP2), the essential PM instructional content is being developed. The PreMETS consortium has meticulously prepared and assessed WP2. The course is designed to equip participants with the necessary understanding and competencies to grasp and implement PM principles and techniques. Moreover, it aims to furnish educators with sufficient knowledge and support to effectively impart the curriculum. The course covers:

- The creation of a PM instructional toolkit that aligns with both tertiary and vocational education benchmarks. This toolkit is segmented into six distinct Working Modules (WM), encapsulating the entire spectrum of PM.
- The provision of an exhaustive toolkit for instructors, catering to academic and vocational levels, to boost the accessibility and efficacy of PM training.
- The introduction of a certification framework and skill verification processes, conferring formal recognition and credentials for PM expertise.
- The formulation of Predictive manufacturing toolkit content, subject to peer evaluation.

Trainees who successfully clear the assessments are anticipated to apply the acquired learning outcomes commensurate with their qualification diploma's level. The modular course's structure will be elaborated in subsequent sections.

Competency-based learning

The modular approach represents an evolving paradigm in educational philosophy, transitioning from conventional teaching to a results-oriented learning framework. This strategy segments the curriculum into concise, standalone modules, each a self-contained unit that doesn't necessarily follow a sequential order. The modular method empowers learners by granting them enhanced control and responsibility over their educational journey. It particularly benefits mature students who possess a more developed capacity for perception.

Central to this approach is the learner-centric model of education, where the student's experience is the focal point of the educational process. Modularization necessitates ongoing tracking and evaluation of student progress within each module. Through

continuous assessment, educators can tailor their teaching strategies in response to the outcomes of these evaluations. This approach also ensures that students receive timely feedback and direction for further improvement.

Key aspects of the modular approach include:

- Integrating assessment activities as core components of the learning experience, such as through the use of multiple-choice questions.
- Offering continual support and feedback to students throughout their educational path, rather than solely post-completion of tasks.
- Motivating students to proactively manage and oversee their own learning process.

Assessment within this framework involves the systematic collection of evidence and subsequent judgment to ascertain whether a student has attained the necessary competency. This verification process ensures that individuals can meet the professional standards demanded in the workplace, as outlined in a training package or a vocational education and training (VET) accredited course.

The modular system facilitates independent assessments for each Working Module (WM). For knowledge evaluation, digital assessment tools like multiple-choice questionnaires are employed to gauge factual understanding. This, however, necessitates the adoption of e-learning technologies.

Digital tools in education

E-learning tools have revolutionized how we approach education and training, presenting numerous benefits that cater to both accessibility and engagement:

- **Convenience and Adaptability:** E-learning platforms enable learners to access educational content from any location at any time, providing a level of convenience that suits individuals with varying schedules or geographical constraints. This adaptability supports self-paced learning, accommodating users in their professional settings, academic environments, or the comfort of their homes.
- **Diverse Multimedia Tools:** These platforms are enriched with a range of multimedia elements, including video content, interactive simulations, and three-dimensional models. Such resources significantly enrich the educational experience, facilitating a deeper comprehension of intricate concepts through engaging and visual methods.
- **Current and Relevant Content:** With the capability for regular updates, e-learning ensures that learners always have access to the most current and relevant information available. This feature is crucial for maintaining the accuracy and timeliness of educational materials.

Professional profile

This course is tailored for a diverse audience, including students, educators, vocational trainers, and professionals from various sectors such as Aviation, Manufacturing, Shipping, Logistics, and Transportation. It aims to provide comprehensive insights into Predictive Maintenance and its application within different business contexts.

Duration – suggested schedule

The core duration of the course is estimated to 50 contact hours with a workload of at least 124 hours of self-paced study

Suggested self-paced schedule:

EQF Level 4: Intermediate Predictive Maintenance Competences

Duration: 3 Months

Course Format: Virtual Learning

Target Audience: Intermediate learners, typically high school graduates or those with some vocational training.

Month 1

Week 1-2: WN1 - Holistic PM Competences

- Title: Introduction to Holistic Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Basic principles of integrating various competences in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Understand fundamental holistic predictive maintenance concepts.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Introductory booklet, video lectures, basic maintenance software.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, simple WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Introduction to holistic PM competences with simple case studies.
- Presentation: Basic overview with visual aids and storyboard.
- Videos: Introductory lectures on holistic predictive maintenance.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on applying basic holistic PM skills.

Week 3-4: WN2 - Digital Skills Competences for PM

- Title: Digital skills for Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Basic digital skills necessary for predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Develop and apply basic digital skills in predictive maintenance.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, video tutorials, basic maintenance tools.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Simple guide on digital skills for PM.
- Presentation: Basic points with visual aids and storyboard.
- Videos: Tutorials on basic digital tools.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on utilizing basic digital tools.

Month 2

Week 1-2: WN3 - Green Skills Competences for PM

- Title: Sustainable Practices in Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Introduction to sustainable practices in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Apply basic green skills in predictive maintenance.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, case studies, video lectures.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Basics of green skills for PM.
- Presentation: Key points with visual aids and storyboard.
- Videos: Introductory lectures on sustainability in maintenance.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on basic green practices.

Week 3-4: WN4 - Resilience Competences for PM

- Title: Building Resilience in Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Basic strategies for enhancing resilience in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Develop fundamental resilience skills.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, resilience assessment tools, video lectures.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Basic resilience strategies.
- Presentation: Key points with visual aids and storyboard.
- Videos: Introductory resilience lectures.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on resilience skills.

Month 3

Week 1-2: WN5 - Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competences for PM

- Title: Innovation in Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Basics of fostering innovation and entrepreneurial thinking in predictive maintenance.
- Learning Objective: Apply basic innovation and entrepreneurial skills.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, innovation tools, case studies, video links.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Basics of innovation and entrepreneurship in maintenance.
- Presentation: Key points with visual aids and storyboard.
- Videos: Introductory innovation lectures.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.

- Assessment: WebQuest on basic innovation skills.

Week 3-4: WN6 - Relearning How to Learn in a Digital Environment

- Title: Learning in the Digital Age for Predictive Maintenance
- Description: Techniques for effective learning in a digital environment.
- Learning Objective: Enhance basic digital learning skills.
- Duration: 2 Weeks
- Required Resources: Booklet, digital learning tools, video tutorials.
- Method of Assessment: Multiple-choice quiz, WebQuest.

Components:

- Booklet: Basics of digital learning techniques.
- Presentation: Key points with visual aids and storyboard.
- Videos: Basic digital learning tutorials.
- Quiz: 5 multiple-choice questions.
- Assessment: WebQuest on digital learning techniques.

Structure of the Predictive Maintenance course

The course is structured into six subjects (WN), each dedicated to a specific topic and with a defined learning objective. Each session includes the following components:

- A title, a description, a learning objective, a duration, a list of required resources, and a method of assessment.
- A booklet providing as much detail as possible with proper literature.
- A detailed presentation of the material depicting the key points of the booklet. A brief framework (storyboard) is also included in the material.
- A list with video links presenting the main concepts and theories related to the topic.
- A multiple-choice quiz, testing the students' understanding and retention of the topic.
- An assessment (WebQuest), requiring the students to apply the knowledge and skills acquired on the topic to a simulated situation. It also examines the critical thinking of the students.
- Peer feedback enables the learners to give and receive constructive feedback on their projects.

Successful participation in the course requires a high level of proficiency in the course language, along with a basic understanding of data science.

- WN1: Holistic PM Competences
- WN2: Digital Skills Competences for PM
- WN3: Green Skills Competences for PM
- WN4: Resilience Competences for PM
- WN5: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competences for PM
- WN6: Relearning How to Learn in a Digital Environment

Section II: Theoretical and Practical Education

Course educational outcomes

QUALIFICATION	EQF LEVEL	KNOWLEDGES	SKILLS
Predictive Maintenance Course (VET)	4	<p>Technical Knowledge: Solid foundation in the technical aspects of predictive maintenance, including the use of modern tools and technologies.</p> <p>Interdisciplinary Skills: Ability to integrate knowledge from various disciplines to enhance maintenance strategies.</p> <p>Practical Application: Hands-on experience and practical skills to apply predictive maintenance techniques in real-world scenarios.</p> <p>Communication Skills: Effective communication with team members, stakeholders, and other professionals involved in maintenance activities.</p>	<p>Technical Skills: Proficiency in technical aspects of predictive maintenance, including the use of modern tools and technologies.</p> <p>Interdisciplinary Integration: Ability to integrate knowledge from various fields to improve maintenance strategies.</p> <p>Practical Application: Applying theoretical knowledge to real-world maintenance scenarios.</p> <p>Communication Skills: Effectively communicating with team members and stakeholders involved in maintenance activities.</p>

Predictive Maintenance training program - Modules	Recommended contact hours	Estimated Workload
WN1: Holistic PM competences	10	24
WN2: Digital skills competences for PM	9	22
WN3: Green skills competences for PM	9.5	24
WN4: Resilience competences for PM	9.5	24
WN5: Innovation and entrepreneurship competences for PM	6	15
WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment	6	15
Total	50	124

Module Description

WN1 Module: Holistic PM competences

Module WN1: Holistic PM competences		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Types of Predictive Maintenance Technologies • Data Acquisition and Management • Integration of IoT, AI, Machine Learning and Industry 4.0 • Predictive Maintenance Software and Tools • Regulatory Compliance and Safety Standards • Implementation Strategies, Case Studies and Real-World Applications for Predictive Maintenance Optimization • Future Trends in Predictive Maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operational Efficiency • Critical thinking • Project & Time management • Continuous Learning • Analytical problem-solving • Equipment handling & digital tools • Decision-making • Technical writing • Algorithmic, statistical, and programming skills 	10

Learning nodes of WN1 Module: Holistic PM competences

Module WN1: Holistic PM competences	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN1.1 Introduction to Maintenance Methodologies	0.5
WN1.2 Sensor Technologies & Data Analysis	1.5
WN1.3 Asset Optimization, Monitoring & Reporting Models	2
WN1.4 Structural Assessment Methods & Remote Infrastructure Management	3.5
WN1.5 Forecasting Systems	2.5
Total	10
WORKLOAD	24

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN1.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Outline of main aspects of predictive maintenance ● Description of different Predictive Maintenance Methodologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding the foundation of predictive maintenance in a holistic context ● Outline different methodologies
WN1.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Basic principles, key types, future trends of Sensing Technologies plus their role in PM. ● Data analysis through statistical methods and physics-based models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Describe basic principles of Sensing Technologies and their role in PM ● Name foundational statistical methods and physics-based models
WN1.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Foundation on time management systems in PM ● Reporting Models in PM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding time-management as a necessary factor in PM ● Naming reporting models used in PM
WN1.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Commonly used structural assessment methods ● Popular predictive maintenance software solutions and platforms ● Emerging trends and innovations in predictive maintenance, such as advancements in AI and machine learning, edge computing, and AR/VR. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Naming commonly used structural assessment methods ● Naming popular predictive maintenance software solutions and platforms ● Outlining emerging trends and innovations in PM
WN1.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Statistical techniques and machine learning algorithms used in predictive maintenance ● Data Analysis techniques 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understanding statistical techniques and machine learning algorithms used in PM ● Naming basic data analysis techniques

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction of Unplanned Downtime and Asset Health Management • Cost-benefit analysis to justify predictive maintenance investments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predicting unplanned downtime and manage asset health management • Outline a cost-benefit analysis
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WN1 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

WN2 Module: Digital skills competences for PM

Module WN2: Digital Skills Competences for PM		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core principles of PM and its role in optimizing industrial processes. • Different types of PM techniques (condition-based, predictive, etc.) and their applications. • Benefits of PM (cost reduction, improved efficiency, safety, increased equipment lifespan). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the value proposition of PM to diverse stakeholders (engineers, managers, technicians). • Distinguish between various PM techniques and their appropriate uses in different industrial settings. • Use basic PM terminology correctly when discussing concepts, techniques, and data. 	9

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Basic terminology and concepts in PM (e.g., failure modes, root cause analysis, asset health). • Different data types used in PM (vibration, temperature, oil analysis, etc.) and their significance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interpret basic PM reports and data visualizations. • Identify suitable sensors for specific PM applications based on the type of data needed. 	
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Learning nodes of WN2 Module: Digital skills competences for PM

Module WN2: Digital skills competences for PM	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN2.1 Introduction to PM	0.5
WN2.2 Data Collection	2
WN2.3 Data Analysis	4
WN2.4 Maintenance Strategies	1
WN2.5 Communication and Collaboration	1
WN2.6 Emerging Technologies	0.5
Total	9
WORKLOAD	22

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN2.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core principles of PM and its role in optimizing industrial processes. • Different types of PM techniques (condition-based, predictive, etc.) and their applications. • Benefits of PM (cost reduction, improved efficiency, safety, increased equipment lifespan). • Basic terminology and concepts in PM (e.g., failure modes, root cause analysis, asset health). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the value proposition of PM to diverse stakeholders (engineers, managers, technicians). • Distinguish between various PM techniques and their appropriate uses in different industrial settings. • Use basic PM terminology correctly when discussing concepts, techniques, and data.
WN2.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different data types used in PM (vibration, temperature, oil analysis, etc.) and their significance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify suitable sensors for specific PM applications based on the type of data needed.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Various sensors used in PM (accelerometers, thermocouples, oil debris sensors, etc.) and their working principles. • Data acquisition techniques and methods (manual, automated, continuous, periodic). • Basic principles of signal processing (sampling, filtering, noise reduction). • The role of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) in PM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect and organize PM data from various sources (sensors, databases, etc.) into a usable format. • Perform basic signal processing tasks on PM data (e.g., filtering, normalization) to improve data quality. • Connect and integrate sensors with IIoT systems for real-time data collection and monitoring. • Troubleshoot basic issues with data collection processes (sensor malfunctions, connectivity problems).
WN2.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical methods for data analysis relevant to PM (e.g., descriptive statistics, regression analysis, time series analysis). • The concept of feature extraction and its importance in PM. • Anomaly detection techniques (e.g., threshold-based, statistical, machine learning-based). • Data visualization principles for effective communication of PM results. • The role of machine learning in PM (e.g., classification, regression, clustering). • Basic understanding of data cleaning and preprocessing (e.g., missing data imputation, outlier removal). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyze PM data using statistical tools (e.g., Excel, Python libraries) to identify trends, correlations, and patterns. • Perform feature extraction on PM data to identify relevant characteristics for analysis. • Apply anomaly detection techniques to identify potential equipment failures or deviations from normal operating conditions. • Create meaningful visualizations of PM data (e.g., charts, graphs, dashboards) to communicate findings clearly. • Apply basic machine learning algorithms to PM problems (e.g., predicting remaining useful life). • Clean and preprocess data to ensure its quality and suitability for analysis.
WN2.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Condition-based maintenance strategies (e.g., vibration analysis, oil analysis). • Predictive maintenance strategies (e.g., using machine learning models for failure prediction). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and implement condition-based maintenance strategies based on PM data. • Implement predictive maintenance strategies using machine learning models or other techniques.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Remaining useful life (RUL) estimation techniques. • The role of PM in developing effective maintenance plans and schedules. • The concept of asset health management and how PM contributes to it. • The integration of PM with other maintenance approaches (e.g., preventive maintenance). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimate the remaining useful life of assets based on PM data and analysis. • Create and optimize maintenance plans and schedules based on PM insights. • Utilize PM data to assess and manage the health of assets throughout their lifecycle. • Integrate PM with existing maintenance systems and workflows to optimize overall maintenance effectiveness.
WN2.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of effective communication and collaboration in PM. • Reporting and presenting PM findings to various stakeholders (technical and non-technical). • Data sharing and visualization tools for collaboration (e.g., dashboards, cloud-based platforms). • The role of documentation in PM (e.g., maintenance logs, work orders). • Collaboration with IT and maintenance teams on PM projects. • Communication protocols (e.g., OPC UA) for data exchange between machines and systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effectively communicate PM findings to diverse stakeholders, including engineers, technicians, and managers, using clear and concise language. • Create professional reports and presentations that clearly communicate PM results and recommendations. • Utilize data sharing and visualization tools to collaborate with colleagues and stakeholders on PM projects. • Maintain accurate and comprehensive documentation of PM processes, results, and recommendations. • Effectively collaborate with IT and maintenance teams to ensure successful implementation and operation of PM systems. • Understand the basics of communication protocols used in PM and their role in enabling data exchange between systems.
WN2.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The role of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in PM (e.g., deep learning, reinforcement learning). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply AI and ML techniques to PM problems (e.g., predictive modeling, anomaly detection).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concept of digital twins and their applications in PM. • The potential use of blockchain technology in PM (e.g., for data security, traceability). • Augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) applications in PM (e.g., for training, maintenance procedures). • Future trends and advancements in PM technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work with digital twin models to simulate and optimize PM strategies. • Understand the potential benefits and limitations of blockchain technology in the context of PM. • Explore the use of AR/VR technologies for training and assisting technicians in PM tasks. • Stay up-to-date with the latest trends and developments in PM technologies through continuous learning and professional development.
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WN2 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards (ppt).
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

WN3 Module: Green skills competences for PM

Module WN3: Green skills competences		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability Practices: Knowledge of sustainable maintenance practices that 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable Practices Implementation: Applying sustainable and environmentally friendly maintenance practices. 	9.5

<p>minimize environmental impact.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Efficiency: Skills to implement and maintain systems that are energy-efficient and environmentally friendly. • Waste Management: Understanding of how to manage and reduce waste generated from maintenance activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Management: Skills to enhance energy efficiency in maintenance operations. • Waste Reduction: Techniques to manage and minimize waste generated from maintenance activities. 	
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Learning nodes of WN3 Module: Green skills competences for PM

Module WN3: Green Skills competences	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN3.1 Integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Principles in Manufacturing	1
WN3.2 Introduction to GHG Emissions, Global Agreements Corporate Accountability and Reporting	0.5
WN3.3 Life Cycle Assessment: Theory, Methods, and Practical Applications	1
WN3.4 Renewable Energy and Sustainable Manufacturing Practices	4
WN3.5 Sustainable Manufacturing and Resource Efficiency	3
Total	9.5
WORKLOAD	24

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
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WN3.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESG Principles and their significance in modern manufacturing • Environmental Considerations • Social Responsibility • Ethical business practices • Emerging trends in ESG practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to name ESG principles and discuss their significance in modern manufacturing • Understanding of environmental considerations in PM • Foundational skills in linking social responsibility to PM • Outlining Ethical business practices in PM • Naming emerging trends in ESG practices
WN3.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GHG emissions and their contributing factors to climate change • International agreements and frameworks • Financial and cost accounting principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the principles of GHG emissions • Naming applicable international agreements and frameworks that influence PM • Outlining financial and cost accounting principles applicable for PM
WN3.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable development • Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) • Different Life Cycle Inventory methods and their applications • Benefits and limitations of LCA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the principles of sustainable development • Name the key stages of the LCA • Outlining different LCI methods and their applications • Critically evaluate the benefits and limitations of utilizing LCA in PM
WN3.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energy sources • Benefits and challenges associated with renewable energy adoption • Energy-efficient practices and their impact on sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Naming various renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro and biomass • Critically evaluate benefits and challenges associated with renewable energy adoption

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy frameworks and regulations supporting renewable energy integration and sustainability initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outlining policy frameworks and regulation supporting renewable energy integration and sustainability initiatives
WN3.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental challenges faced by industries • Sustainable practices • Innovative research methods • Circular Economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outlining environmental challenges faced by industries • Naming sustainable practices in PM • Foundational skills in innovative research methods • Understanding circular economy basics

WN3 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards (ppt).
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

WN4 Module: Resilience competences for PM

Module WN4: Resilience competences		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Management: Ability to identify, assess, and mitigate risks associated with maintenance activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment: Identifying and assessing risks in maintenance activities. 	9.5

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability: Skills to adapt maintenance strategies in response to changing conditions and unforeseen challenges. • Stress Management: Techniques to handle stress and maintain performance under pressure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability: Adapting maintenance strategies to changing conditions and unexpected challenges. • Stress Management: Techniques to manage stress and maintain high performance under pressure. 	
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Learning nodes of WN4 Module: Resilience competences for PM

Module WN4: Resilience Competences	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN4.1 Core Principles and Strategic Resilience in Predictive Maintenance	1
WN4.2 Advanced Technological Integration in Maintenance	3.5
WN4.3 Safety, Risk Assessment, and Structural Integrity	1
WN4.4 Competencies for Maintenance Professionals	1
WN4.5 Future Trends and Professional Development in Predictive Maintenance	3
Total	9.5
WORKLOAD	24

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN4.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concepts and benefits of Predictive Maintenance • Significance of resilience competences (RC) in maintaining continuous operations. • Strategies for continuous improvement and adaptation in maintenance practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the core principles of PM and resilience competences. • Outline the effectiveness of maintenance strategies in the context of resilience. • Name strategic solutions to improve operational performance and safety. • Understand case studies to understand the practical implications of PM.

WN4.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in automating maintenance processes. • The application of IoT devices and sensors in real-time monitoring. • Advanced monitoring tools in predictive maintenance. • The use of forecasting analytics in predicting maintenance needs. • Data integration and analysis for proactive maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the significance of AI and ML in automating maintenance processes • Demonstrate the use IoT devices for real-time data collection and monitoring. • Name advanced monitoring tools to enhance predictive maintenance strategies. • Understanding forecasting models to anticipate maintenance requirements. • Conduct basic data integration and analysis for PM
WN4.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human safety systems in maintenance operations. • Various risk assessment tools and their applications in proactive maintenance. • Methods for identifying safety hazards in maintenance. • Strategies for effective risk mitigation and management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify safety systems and protocols in maintenance tasks. • Naming risk assessments using tools like FMEA, HAZOP, and RCA. • Apply effective risk mitigation strategies to prevent failures. • Outline best practices for maintaining safety and minimizing hazards in maintenance operations.
WN4.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptability and problem-solving in maintenance roles • Technical proficiency and stress management. • Effective communication and teamwork. • Attention to detail and effective time management in maintenance. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the need to adapt quickly to changes and solve complex maintenance issues effectively. • Demonstrate technical expertise in handling and maintaining equipment. • Communicate clearly and concisely with team members and stakeholders.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage time efficiently to adhere to maintenance schedules and priorities.
WN4.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future technological changes and their possible impact on predictive maintenance. • Evolving skills requirements for staying competitive in the maintenance field. • Integration of sustainability and ethical considerations in maintenance practices. • Fostering innovation and adaptability in maintenance operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify new technologies and methodologies in predictive maintenance. • Evaluate skills that align with future industry trends. • Incorporate sustainability and ethical considerations in maintenance strategies. • Utilize a culture of innovation and strategic thinking to address future challenges.

WN4 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

WN5 Module: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definitions of innovation and entrepreneurship in the context of industrial maintenance. • Types of innovation (incremental, disruptive, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the importance of innovation and entrepreneurial thinking in the context of PM and its potential to drive efficiency and cost savings. 	6

<p>etc.) and their relevance to PM.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key concepts in entrepreneurship (opportunity recognition, risk management, value creation). • The role of digital technologies (AI, IoT, etc.) in fostering innovation in PM. • Techniques for generating innovative ideas for PM (e.g., brainstorming, design thinking). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify opportunities for innovation within existing PM processes and technologies. • Analyze the potential risks and rewards associated with innovative PM solutions. • Utilize digital tools and platforms to research and stay informed about the latest trends and developments in PM innovation. • Apply creative problem-solving techniques to generate innovative PM solutions. 	
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Learning nodes of WN5 Module: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN5.1 Introduction to Innovation and Entrepreneurship in PM	2
WN5.2 Idea Generation and Evaluation	1
WN5.3 Business Model Development	1.5
WN5.4 Team Building and Leadership	0.5
WN5.5 Project Management and Implementation	1
Total	6
WORKLOAD	15

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN5.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definitions of innovation and entrepreneurship in the context of industrial maintenance. • Types of innovation (incremental, disruptive, etc.) and their relevance to PM. • Key concepts in entrepreneurship (opportunity recognition, risk management, value creation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the importance of innovation and entrepreneurial thinking in the context of PM and its potential to drive efficiency and cost savings. • Identify opportunities for innovation within existing PM processes and technologies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The role of digital technologies (AI, IoT, etc.) in fostering innovation in PM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the potential risks and rewards associated with innovative PM solutions. Utilize digital tools and platforms to research and stay informed about the latest trends and developments in PM innovation.
WN5.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Techniques for generating innovative ideas for PM (e.g., brainstorming, design thinking). Criteria for evaluating the potential impact and feasibility of PM innovations. Understanding of intellectual property (IP) rights and their importance in protecting PM innovations. The concept of minimum viable product (MVP) and its role in testing and validating PM ideas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Apply creative problem-solving techniques to generate innovative PM solutions. Critically evaluate the feasibility and potential impact of different PM ideas, considering factors such as technical complexity, cost-effectiveness, and market demand. Conduct basic market research to assess the potential demand and competition for a PM innovation. Develop a basic business plan or proposal outlining the value proposition, target market, and revenue model for a PM innovation.
WN5.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key components of a business model for a PM innovation (value proposition, customer segments, revenue streams, etc.). Different types of business models relevant to PM (e.g., product-as-a-service, subscription-based, licensing). Strategies for marketing and selling PM innovations to different stakeholders (e.g., industrial companies, maintenance service providers). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a comprehensive business model for a PM innovation, detailing the key components and demonstrating its financial viability. Identify potential funding sources for a PM innovation (e.g., grants, venture capital, crowdfunding). Create a marketing plan for a PM innovation, outlining the target audience, messaging, and channels.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The role of data analytics in developing and optimizing business models for PM innovations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilize data analytics to refine the business model and make informed decisions about pricing, distribution, and customer engagement.
WN5.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of building effective teams for developing and implementing PM innovations. • Leadership styles and their impact on innovation and team performance. • Strategies for fostering a culture of innovation within a team. • The role of communication and collaboration in driving innovation and entrepreneurship in PM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build and lead a multidisciplinary team to develop and implement a PM innovation. • Demonstrate effective leadership skills, such as communication, delegation, and conflict resolution, to motivate and guide a PM innovation team. • Create a positive and supportive team environment that encourages creativity, risk-taking, and collaboration. • Communicate effectively with team members, stakeholders, and potential customers to build support and buy-in for a PM innovation.
WN5.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project management methodologies for PM innovation projects (e.g., Agile, Waterfall). • Key stages in the implementation of PM innovations (e.g., pilot testing, scaling, continuous improvement). • Risk management strategies for PM innovation projects. • The importance of monitoring and evaluation in ensuring the success of PM innovations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a project plan for a PM innovation, outlining the timeline, milestones, and resource allocation. • Manage the implementation of a PM innovation, ensuring that it meets the project goals and objectives. • Identify and mitigate potential risks that could impact the success of a PM innovation project. • Monitor and evaluate the performance of a PM innovation, using data to identify areas for

		improvement and optimize its impact.
WN5.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal frameworks and regulations relevant to PM innovation (e.g., data protection, intellectual property, safety standards). • Ethical considerations in the development and implementation of PM innovations (e.g., data privacy, algorithm bias, impact on jobs). • Corporate social responsibility (CSR) and its role in promoting sustainable and responsible innovation in PM. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that a PM innovation complies with all relevant legal and regulatory requirements. • Address ethical concerns related to PM innovations, such as data privacy and the potential impact on employment. • Develop and implement a CSR strategy for a PM innovation, ensuring that it aligns with the company's values and contributes to the broader social and environmental goals.

WN5 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

WN6 Module: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment

Module WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment		
Knowledge	Skills	Contact hours
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Steps involved in implementing a PM program (planning, resource allocation, training, etc.). Strategies for managing and sustaining a PM program (continuous improvement, performance evaluation, change management). The role of leadership and organizational culture in the success of PM initiatives. Integration of PM with other maintenance strategies (e.g., preventive maintenance, corrective maintenance). Ethical considerations in PM (data privacy, cybersecurity, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a comprehensive plan for implementing a PM program within an organization. Evaluate the effectiveness of a PM program and identify areas for improvement. Communicate the benefits of PM to different stakeholders and build support for the program. Select and implement appropriate PM software and tools to support the program. Ensure compliance with relevant regulations and standards related to PM. 	6

Learning nodes of WN6 Module: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment

Module WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment	RECOMMENDED CONTACT HOURS
Topics – Learning nodes	
WN6.1 Introduction to Digital Learning in PM	2
WN6.2 Effective Learning Strategies in a Digital Environment	1
WN6.3 Digital Collaboration and Communication for PM	0.5
WN6.4 Digital Tools for PM Learning and Practice	0.5
WN6.5 Staying Current with Digital PM Trends	1
WN6.6 Personal Branding and Digital Presence	1
Total	6
WORKLOAD	15

Topic	Knowledges	Skills
WN6.1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The changing landscape of learning in the digital age and its implications for PM professionals. ● The importance of continuous learning and upskilling in the rapidly evolving field of PM. ● Key digital learning resources and platforms relevant to PM (e.g., online courses, webinars, forums, communities of practice). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Articulate the benefits and challenges of learning in a digital environment for PM professionals. ● Identify personal learning goals and develop a plan to achieve them in the context of PM. ● Utilize various digital learning resources and platforms to access relevant information and knowledge on PM.
WN6.2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Different learning styles and how to adapt them to a digital learning environment. ● Time management and organization techniques for successful digital learning. ● Critical thinking and problem-solving skills in a digital context. ● The role of self-directed learning and metacognition in maximizing learning outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Apply effective learning strategies (e.g., spaced repetition, active recall) to enhance knowledge retention and skill acquisition in PM. ● Manage time effectively and prioritize learning activities to balance work, personal life, and professional development in PM. ● Evaluate the credibility and relevance of information obtained from digital sources. ● Apply critical thinking and problem-solving skills to real-world PM challenges encountered in digital resources (e.g., case studies, simulations).
WN6.3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The importance of collaboration and communication in a digital learning environment. ● Tools and platforms for online collaboration and communication (e.g., video conferencing, project management software, shared documents). ● Effective communication strategies for digital environments (e.g., email etiquette, virtual presentations). ● The role of networking and building professional relationships in a digital context. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participate actively in online discussions and forums related to PM, sharing knowledge and insights with peers. ● Collaborate effectively with peers and instructors in a digital environment to complete group projects and assignments related to PM. ● Use digital communication tools effectively to interact with peers, instructors, and industry experts in PM. ● Build a professional network online by connecting with peers, instructors, and industry experts in

		PM through social media and professional platforms.
WN6.4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Essential digital tools for PM professionals (e.g., data analysis software, simulation software, programming environments). Online simulation platforms for practicing PM skills in a safe and controlled environment. Programming languages and tools for automating PM tasks and processes. Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) tools for PM training and visualization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilize data analysis software (e.g., Excel, Python, R) to analyze PM data and extract insights. Use simulation software to practice PM techniques and strategies in a virtual environment. Apply programming skills (e.g., Python) to automate data analysis, visualization, and reporting tasks in PM. Explore the potential of VR/AR technologies for PM training and visualization, experiencing virtual simulations and interactive environments related to PM concepts and practices.
WN6.5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The importance of staying up-to-date with the latest digital trends and technologies in PM. Strategies for continuous learning and professional development in the digital age (e.g., online courses, certifications, webinars, conferences). The role of professional networks and communities of practice in staying current with PM developments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regularly review industry publications, blogs, and news sources to stay informed about the latest trends and developments in PM technologies and practices. Participate in online courses, webinars, and conferences to enhance PM knowledge and skills. Engage with professional networks and communities of practice online to exchange knowledge and collaborate with other PM professionals.
WN6.6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The importance of personal branding and a strong digital presence for career advancement in PM. Strategies for creating a compelling online portfolio and resume highlighting PM expertise. Effective communication and networking strategies in a digital environment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a professional online profile showcasing PM skills and experience. Utilize social media platforms (e.g., LinkedIn) to network with other PM professionals and share knowledge and insights. Participate in online discussions and contribute to PM forums and communities to demonstrate expertise and build a reputation in the field.

WN6 Learning approach

- Video presentation with slides containing the whole module content (all topics), plus 50 slides of content summary provided for self-paced learning.
- A detailed booklet is provided to the student to study the content presented in self-paced mode.
- Set of 5 assessment multiple choice questions for knowledge comprehension.
- Interconnection of different topics and focus areas with illustrative storyboards.
- Scheduled Q&A sessions between learners and teachers/tutors via forum page inside PreMETS platform within the piloting phase of WP5.
- Additional video list including industry expert talks, real case studies, PM applications and practical examples for each topic.
- Hands-on field visits from external stakeholders demonstrating PM tools and technologies in collaboration with PreMETS trainers (during project implementation will be done in 2 pilot sites; Romania & Greece).
- Project-based learning via an individual assignment (described within WebQuest document) to develop a PM plan for their company or a hypothetical organization.

Section III: Examination and Qualification

Examination Planning

The examination objectives are designed to align seamlessly with the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance course's learning outcomes for EQF level 4 compliant skills and knowledge, across various modules:

- WN1: Holistic PM Competences
- WN2: Digital Skills Competences for PM
- WN3: Green Skills Competences for PM
- WN4: Resilience Competences for PM
- WN5: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competences for PM
- WN6: Relearning How to Learn in a Digital Environment

Each module will employ appropriate digital assessment formats, such as multiple-choice questions for factual knowledge.

- 5 questions from the WP2 assessment questionnaire will be training questions and tasks will be developed to test both theoretical understanding and practical application.
- 25 questions (WP2) that are diverse and inclusive, catering to different learning styles and digital proficiency levels will be used as assessment and certification questions.

PreMETS microcredential certifications are tailored around the Europass Digital Credentials framework to take these EU instruments to the next pan-EU level.

PreMETS' micro-credential modules are linked to the ECVET4 level courses.

PreMETS Digital Certificate will be issued.

Course Objective:

To provide intermediate learners with foundational knowledge and skills in preventive maintenance, enabling them to perform routine maintenance tasks, understand basic maintenance principles, and use basic digital tools for maintenance purposes.

Examination Objectives:

1. Understanding Predictive Maintenance Basics:
 - Define preventive maintenance and explain its importance.
 - Identify different types of preventive maintenance activities.
2. Routine Maintenance Tasks:
 - Demonstrate the ability to perform routine maintenance tasks on basic machinery and equipment.
 - List common tools and materials used in preventive maintenance and describe their uses.
3. Maintenance Scheduling:
 - Explain the concept of maintenance scheduling and its benefits.
 - Create a simple maintenance schedule for a piece of equipment.

4. Safety and Compliance:
 - Identify safety hazards associated with maintenance tasks.
 - Describe safety measures and compliance standards relevant to preventive maintenance.
5. Digital Tools and Record Keeping:
 - Use basic digital tools to log maintenance activities.
 - Demonstrate how to use maintenance management software for scheduling and tracking maintenance tasks.
6. Problem-Solving and Decision Making:
 - Apply basic troubleshooting techniques to identify common equipment issues.
 - Make simple decisions based on maintenance data and equipment condition.
7. Assessment Methods:
 - Multiple-choice quizzes to test theoretical knowledge.
 - A project or assignment involving the creation of a maintenance schedule.

Examination Scheduling

Examinations will be available online, on the PreMETS platform after the completion of each module.

Specific time limits for different sections of the exam will be defined based on their complexity and the expected time required for completion.

Examination Administration

PreMETS platform will be used for learning and examination purposes. It includes a reliable Learning Management System (LMS) and hosts a specialized examination software that was developed under the micro credential certification framework task. It will be utilized to support secure test-taking, question randomization, and time management. As well as automated certification or re-examination process.

Detailed instructions about the examination process, rules, and technical requirements will be provided prior to the exam on the PreMETS platform.

A clear protocol for trainees to report and resolve issues during the examination will be established, including contingency plans for extended time or rescheduling if technical problems occur, all information will be public on the platform.

Examination Execution and Processes

Digital submissions will be automatically generated, collected and secured within the LMS from the PreMETS platform.

Data will be backed up and protected against unauthorized access.

Automated tools will be used for objective questions, and detailed rubrics will be provided for subjective assessments to ensure consistency and fairness in grading.

Post-training monitoring recommendations and continuous learning suggestions will be provided.

Results compilation and distribution

Results will be analyzed to identify trends, areas for improvement, and achievements.

Analytics tools provided by the LMS will be used to assess performance comprehensively.

A PreMETS Digital Certificate will be prepared and distributed through the LMS, verifying successful course completion and mastery of specific skills.

Evaluation of Results

Both written and practical examinations (where applicable) will be conducted for the award of the applicable PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate.

Feedback from trainees will be collected to help improve the course and teaching process.

A questionnaire will be developed and given to trainees at the end of the course to collect their opinions and impressions on the competences and knowledge acquired, as well as to identify possible areas for improvement.

Participants in the training program are eligible to take the examination if they can demonstrate attendance of at least 70% of the lessons. Participants who achieve 70% correct answers will be granted the PreMETS Predictive Maintenance Digital Certificate.

Written Examination:

For each module, the written examination will consist of multiple-choice questions, with a minimum of one question per recommended teaching hour.

Each question will have one correct answer among four proposed answers, and candidates will have between 1 and 5 minutes to answer each question, depending on its complexity.

Evaluation Performance:

To pass a Module's examination, candidates must achieve at least 70% of the maximum possible mark.

Re-examination:

Failure in any individual module of the examination will require re-examination only in the module failed. Candidates who fail any module three times must retake the classes (videos and training materials) and the examination of the failed micro-credential module.

Appendix I: EQF Framework

EQF Level	Knowledge	Skills	Responsibility and Autonomy
	<i>In the context of EQF, knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual</i>	<i>In the context of EQF, skills are described as cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive and creative thinking) and practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools and instruments)</i>	<i>In the context of the EQF responsibility and autonomy is described as the ability of the learner to apply knowledge and skills autonomously and with responsibility</i>
8	Knowledge at the most advanced frontier of a field of work or study and at the interface between fields	The most advanced and specialised skills and techniques, including synthesis and evaluation, required to solve critical problems in research and/or innovation and to extend and redefine existing knowledge or professional practice	Demonstrate substantial authority, innovation, autonomy, scholarly and professional integrity and sustained commitment to the development of new ideas or processes at the forefront of work or study contexts including research
7	Highly specialised knowledge, some of which is at the forefront of knowledge in a field of work or study, as the basis for original thinking and/or research Critical awareness of knowledge issues in a field and at the interface between different fields	Specialised problem-solving skills required in research and/or innovation in order to develop new knowledge and procedures and to integrate knowledge from different fields	Manage and transform work or study contexts that are complex, unpredictable and require new strategic approaches; take responsibility for contributing to professional knowledge and practice and/or for reviewing the strategic performance of teams
6	Advanced knowledge of a field of work or study, involving a critical understanding of theories and principles	Advanced skills, demonstrating mastery and innovation, required to solve complex and unpredictable problems in a specialised field of work or study	Manage complex technical or professional activities or projects, taking responsibility for decision-making in unpredictable work or study contexts; take responsibility for managing professional development of individuals and groups
5	Comprehensive, specialised, factual and theoretical knowledge within a field of work or study and an awareness of the boundaries of that knowledge	A comprehensive range of cognitive and practical skills required to develop creative solutions to abstract problems	Exercise management and supervision in contexts of work or study activities where there is unpredictable change; review and develop performance of self and others
4	Factual and theoretical knowledge in broad contexts within a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to generate solutions to specific problems in a field of work or study	Exercise self-management within the guidelines of work or study contexts that are usually predictable, but are subject to change; supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities
3	Knowledge of facts, principles, processes and general concepts, in a field of work or study	A range of cognitive and practical skills required to accomplish tasks and solve problems by selecting and applying basic methods, tools, materials and information	Take responsibility for completion of tasks in work or study; adapt own behaviour to circumstances in solving problems
2	Basic factual knowledge of a field of work or study	Basic cognitive and practical skills required to use relevant information in order to carry out tasks and to solve routine problems using simple rules and tools	Work or study under supervision with some autonomy
1	Basic general knowledge	Basic skills required to carry out simple tasks	Work or study under direct supervision in a structured context

Description of the eight EQF levels - <https://europass.europa.eu/en/description-eight-eqf-levels>

Figure 1: Description of EQF levels. [Online: Available: <https://europass.europa.eu/en/description-eight-eqf-levels>]

Appendix II: PM training toolkit VET certification strategy language translations

D2.3 – PM training toolkit VET certification strategy report has been translated in Romanian, Greek, Italian, German, Dutch and Serbian. A link to these translated documents can be found below.

D2.3 – PM training toolkit VET certification strategy (Language translations)

Link:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TJOyeUcHm49kajCJi6b7qwD18vwQJcTs?usp=sharing>

PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Co-funded by
the European Union

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